

Protocol for an assessment of how species richness promotes plant productivity via suppressing plant antagonists.

Registration:

This protocol was developed prior to data extraction and analysis in 2002. Deviations from this protocol in any final publication will be the result of suggestion resulting from final peer review. These will be identified in the finalised manuscript.

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Competing interests

All contributors declare that they have no conflicting interests, either financial or non-financial.

Rationale

The diversity-productivity hypothesis assumes that increasing plant species richness can attain greater productivity (Hector *et al.* 1999; Loreau & Hector 2001; Loreau *et al.* 2001; Tilman, Reich & Knops 2006). However, the exact mechanisms that underpin this relationship remain unclear or potentially context specific. One important mechanism that may underpin this effect is the role of increasing plant species richness facilitating the suppressing of plant antagonists positively affecting the overall productivity of the system. In the context of this assessment plant antagonists can include invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, weeds, plant-feeding nematodes, and plant-consuming rodents. The positive effects of plant species richness on plant productivity resulting from the suppressing of such plant antagonists remains unknown on a global scale. The importance of this mechanism for different ecosystems, plant life forms, climatic zones, trophic levels of antagonists and the effect of experimental types in predicting this effect remain unclear. A generalized synthesis is therefore urgently required to identify the research gaps and to shed light on broad trends according to the existing literature.

The goals of this protocol are to outline approaches to undertake a global meta-analysis to assess the impact of increasing plant species richness in suppressing plant antagonists that have resulting impacts on the growth, reproduction and quality resulting in direct damage to tissues of plants.

Concepts and definitions

Key definitions

Plant species richness: A binary variable (zero or one), indicating whether plant species richness had been increased relative to a monoculture or the lowest species control group. This is considered irrespective of the number of plant species added.

Number of added plant species richness: a continuous variable reflecting the number of species richness added by manipulated plant diversity in experimental designs or by natural plant diversity in observational experiments compared to a control group (i.e., monoculture of an individual plant species, or the lowest plant species).

Plant antagonists: An aggregate of invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, weeds, plant-feeding nematodes and plant-consuming rodents that may negatively impact on plant productivity. This is done using the metric developed and presented in Wan *et al.* (2022).

Trophic group: a categorical variable denoting whether the organisms were invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases (plant pathogenic viruses, fungi and bacteria that infested plants and cause damage to plants), weeds (undesirable, unattractive, or troublesome plants in managed ecosystems), plant-feeding nematodes, plant-consuming rodents (e.g., rats and mice that damage crops, pasture, or trees), or plants (e.g., crops, fruits and trees). For each of these trophic groups performance indicators will be used to assess the impact of plant diversity, i.e., effect of plant diversity on other plants, plant antagonists, invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, weeds, plant-feeding nematodes, and plant-consuming rodents.

Response category for plants: Response categories for the plant community are plant growth, plant reproduction, and damage to plants by herbivores.

Response categories for the plant antagonists: i) reproduction, spread and damage of plant diseases; ii) weed growth, reproduction, and diversity (i.e., species richness and Shannon diversity of weeds); iii) reproduction and damage of plant-feeding nematodes; iii) reproduction and damage of plant-consuming rodents.

Ecosystem type: agroecosystems, grasslands, and forests. Note this literature search excludes articles for shrublands, arid ecosystems and aquatic ecosystems.

Plant life form: herbaceous or woody plants.

Experiment type: experiments of plots (i.e., field and common garden experiments) or pots (i.e., experiments with pots, containers, bottles, trays, boxes and tankers).

Climatic zone type: temperate or tropical (data from greenhouse, indoor and laboratory experiments were removed from models including the climatic zone variable).

Objectives

This study, associated literature search, data extraction and analysis will address the following PICO (population, intervention, comparator, and outcome) statement.

Question	What is the effect of increased plant species richness on plant productivity resulting from the presence of plant antagonists (e.g. other plants, invertebrates, diseases or rodents).
Populations	Plants and associated plant antagonists including other plant (e.g. weeds), invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, plant-feeding nematodes, plant-consuming rodents. For each of these trophic groups aggregate performance indicators will be used to assess the impact of plant diversity, i.e., effect of plant diversity on other plants, plant antagonists, invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, weeds, plant-feeding nematodes, and plant-consuming rodents.
Exposures	Experimental manipulation of plant species richness within replicated field based plot experiments or potted plant communities considered to be agroecosystems, grasslands or forests.
Comparators	Plant species richness, number of added plant species and the moderating effect of plant life forms, climatic zones, trophic levels of antagonists and the effect of experimental types.
Outcomes	Response to changing plant diversity will be assessed by quantification of (i) plant growth, reproduction and quality for plant performance; (ii) herbivore growth, reproduction and damage for herbivore performance; (iii) disease reproduction, spread and damage for plant disease performance; (iv) weed growth, reproduction and diversity for weed performance; (v) nematode reproduction and abundance for nematode performance; (vi) rodent reproduction and damage for rodent performance; and (vii) aggregate

indicators covering the performance of herbivores, diseases, weeds, nematodes and rodents for plant antagonist performance. The exact measures derived will depend on individual study designs. A quantitative synthesis using meta-analytical approaches to assess the impacts of increasing plant species richness on the above comparators. This will consider differential responses across different trophic levels within the community (i.e. plants, invertebrates, etc.).

Within this framework aims to test the hypotheses:

1. Increased plant species richness increases plant productivity directly and reduces plant antagonists directly.
2. Increased plant species richness increases plant performance indirectly by suppressing the pressure of plant antagonists.
3. The effects of plant species richness on the two trophic levels and their interactions will vary across different ecosystems, experiment types, plant life forms and climatic zones. This global synthesis might provide insights into future studies to expound the mechanisms how plant species richness affects plants and plant antagonists.

We will assess this goal using a meta-analysis of published literature quantifying these affects. The following protocol outlines the process for the collection of this literature and associated effect sizes used in subsequent analyses, as well as the proposed analytical framework.

This will be achieved by:

- Identify literature reporting effects of increasing plant species richness on plant diversity considering effects across diverse trophic levels.
- Assess these papers for suitability for the extraction of robust treatment differences and measures of error.
- Extract this data and undertake consistency checks to ensure robust data is extracted from the published studies.
- Undertake a quantitative synthesis of the extracted data to address the specific hypotheses outlined above by performing multiple targeted meta-analyses. This will involve approaches including the use of moderator variables as well as data sub-setting to be defined below.

Methods

The following protocol is intended to follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) (Shamseer *et al.* 2015).

Information sources

Studies were selected through a literature search for peer-reviewed primary scientific literature:

- Web of Science Core Collection
- BIOSIS Previews
- Derwent Innovations Index
- KCI-Korean Journal Database
- MEDLINE

This was supplemented with non-peer reviewed journal sources from:

- Preprint Citation Index
- ProQuest™ Dissertations
- Theses Citation Index
- SciELO Citation Index

Search strategy

We used the Boolean search string based on the “TOPIC” searching: ["plant diversity" OR "crop diversity" OR "crop diversification" OR "plant species richness" OR "polyculture" OR "ground cover vegetation" OR "flower strip" OR "strip crop*" OR "grassy field margin" OR "border crop" OR "intercrop*" OR "interplant*"] AND ["plant disease" OR "plant virus" OR "nematode" OR "weed" OR "herbivor*" OR "pest" OR "biological control" OR "rodent" OR "yield" OR "productivity" OR "biomass"]. These search terms were devised following a workshop held at East China University of Science and Technology, Shanghai in April 2019 including authors and other relevant faculty members with expertise in plant ecology, entomology, agroecology and forestry. This search string is to be applied to all search engines described above. Resulting identified studies will be combined and duplicates removed. This literature search was initiated in June 2019 and is finalized in August 2023.

Data management

All data will be managed at School of Pharmacy of East China University of Science and Technology, and School of Life Sciences of Fudan University, Shanghai within customised Access databases developed by Yu-Quan Wang, Liwan Fu, Jie Liu, Nian-Feng Wan.

Relevance screening

Titles and abstracts will be screened to determine whether the articles had a measured response variable relating to the effects of plant species richness on i) the growth, reproduction and damage of invertebrate herbivores; ii) the reproduction, spread and damage of plant disease; iii) the growth, reproduction and diversity of weeds; iv) the reproduction and damage of plant-feeding nematodes; v) the reproduction and damage of plant consuming rodents; and vi) the growth, reproduction and quality of plants.

Eligibility criteria

We will assess all publications within the criteria defined below from 1900 onwards. We consider only English language articles. Following this pre-screening all potential articles are to be assessed for eligibility on the basis of the following criteria: i) the means, standard deviations (or standard errors) and sample sizes of the selected variables could be extracted from the text, tables, figures or supporting files; ii) the measurements of the treatment (higher plant species richness, ≥ 2) and control (single or lowest plant species richness) groups were conducted at the same spatiotemporal scale; and iii) the agricultural practice (e.g., pesticides and fertilizer input) should be the same for the control and the treatment.

To ensure consistency of paper inclusions and exclusions throughout the screening process the eligibility criteria of potential publications within the merged reference list will be assessed by two people working independently. Where both assessors identify studies as being inappropriate for inclusion on the basis of the criteria above, they will be excluded. The reason for exclusion of studies after assessment of the full text will be recorded.

Risk of bias assessment for individual studies

To ensure that individual trends reported in studies were not the result of flawed experimental designs for each paper we will undertake a risk of bias assessment with the aim of excluding studies considered to potentially result in questionable conclusions as to community responses to increasing plant species richness. To reduce within-study sources of bias, typical for studies considering the effects of plant species richness on biodiversity or productivity, we assessed each study for: 1) incomplete outcome data relating to the loss of samples which may cause bias in the effect sizes used in our meta-analysis; 2) consistent identification of randomization of treatment allocations to avoid systematic bias; 3) consistent identification of baseline conditions to which random allocation of treatments occurred to avoid bias resulting from chance allocation to different historic non-pesticide agricultural practices like fertilizer, irrigation, soil tillage etc; 4) consistent spatiotemporal scale of assessment across treatment groups; 6) evidence for selective outcome reporting whereby only a subset of the recorded variables are reported suggesting selection bias in result reporting. Studies not meeting these requirements were excluded. Where studies are considered to have failed on these criteria they were excluded.

Data extraction

Data extraction from the selected publications is to adhere to the following protocol. The preferred data source will be the mean values of multiple sampling dates or years as presented in an individual article. If these mean values were not presented, we used the data of the latest sampling period. For articles that covered more than one experimental location, we will consider these experimental results separately. When numeric values were not provided directly, these will be extracted from figures using the "GetData Graph Digitizer" 2.2642. However, where linear or non-linear relationships between plant species richness and one of these response variables was presented in a figure, these will be extracted via fitted regression equations.

For each study different metrics can be used to quantify plant species richness effects on different trophic groups. We aimed to capture these effects both for the overall plant community, as well as for the individual plant antagonists as measured within studies. We define aggregate performance indicators used to assess the impact of plant diversity on different trophic group, specifically the plant communities as well as the plant antagonists of invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, weeds, plant-feeding nematodes and plant-consuming rodents.

For the plant communities data extraction focused on measures of plant growth, reproduction and quality based on whether there had been foliage or other plant tissue damage by herbivores. Depending on the experiment design of each study If the authors show the data of plant community, we will extract that data at the level of the plant community. If the authors show individual plant data that individual plant data will be extracted, although this will be done so as to avoid repeated sampling from the same study. Specifically, where both community and individual data are available the community data would be used.

For the individual plant antagonist responses to increasing plant species richness data extraction focused on measures of i) herbivore growth, reproduction and damage for herbivore performance; (ii) disease reproduction, spread and damage for plant disease performance; (iii) weed growth, reproduction and diversity for weed performance; (iv) nematode reproduction and abundance for nematode performance; (v) rodent reproduction and damage for rodent performance.

Aggregate indicators for the plant antagonists. Data extraction was also undertaken for the aggregate indicators covering the performance of herbivores, diseases, weeds, nematodes and rodents for plant antagonist performance. The aggregate index for the effect of plant antagonists will follow the approach shown in Wan et al (2022). In summary, the aggregated plant antagonist are obtained by stacking the observations of aggregated herbivore, disease, weed, nematode, rodent performances. The aggregated herbivore, disease, weed, nematode, rodent and plant performances are obtained by stacking the observations of corresponding growth, reproduction, damage/quality. The observations of growth, reproduction, damage/quality are obtained by calculating SMDs (standardized mean difference) or ROMs (log transformed ratio of means) (see below in the stats section) using these measurements in treatment and control groups. Note, these measurements may be different in different studies and so be definition are mixed-scaled, e.g. biomass, density, percentage, etc.

When an article included different levels of plant species richness the control groups was considered to be the treatment with the lowest plant species which would then be compared to the other treatment levels of plant species richness. Where multiple comparisons are present in a study these will be derived and considered as independent paired observations.

Quality checks: Extraction of data from articles is to be undertaken by Y.Q.W., L.F., J.L. and N.F.W. following a joint training process to ensure consistency in application of protocols. This will involve the combined simultaneous assessment of 50 articles to act as a training set to ensure common application of approaches. Following this initial phase regular cross-checking of 1 in every 10 papers is to be performed by another data extractor to ensure consistency in extracted effect sizes. Where inconsistencies were found those 10 papers would be jointly reassessed.

Data analysis

Definition of effect size and its measures

We calculated the Standardized Mean Difference to quantify the plant diversity effects on the various trophic groups as $SMD_i = (M_{ti} - M_{ci})/sd_i$, $1 \leq i \leq m$, in which M_{ti} and M_{ci} were the mean values in the treatment and control groups, respectively, and

$$sd_i = \sqrt{\frac{(n_{ti} - 1) \times sd_{ti}^2 + (n_{ci} - 1) \times sd_{ci}^2}{n_{ti} + n_{ci} - 2}},$$
 in which n_{ti} and n_{ci} were the sample sizes and sd_{ti} and

sd_{ci} were the standard deviations in the two groups, respectively. An unbiased approach was used to estimate the sampling variance. We will use this derived measure of SMD as the response variable for each model.

Meta-regression analysis

We will fit multilevel mixed-effects meta-regression models using the R package Metafor (Viechtbauer 2010) implemented in the latest version of the R Statistical environment Version (R Core Development Team 2022). The effect size metric SMD and ROM will be derived using the function “escalc()” (argument “measure” set to “SMD” for SMD and “ROM” for ROM) with unbiased sample variance estimates constructed with the function “escalc()” (argument “vtype” set to “UB” for SMD while no argument for ROM). Trophic groups and integrated trophic groups (i.e., plants, plant antagonists) were included as fixed effects along with the moderator variables (i.e. ecosystem type, type of experimental study, plant life form, climatic zone, and number of added plant genotypes). The potential effect of plant species will be accounted for all models by adding random intercepts for plant species identity and including the phylogenetic relatedness between plant species as part of the correlation structure. In addition, each effect size will be nested within the corresponding study to incorporate the hierarchical error structure of multiple effects coming from the same study.

For each mixed-effects meta-analysis model, we will first fitted a base model by treating trophic group as the only fixed effect term (Table 1). Following this, the interactions between the trophic group and other predictor variables will be included in the model to assess whether model fit has been improved. This will be assessed using a likelihood-ratio test (LRT). Finally, the trophic group response category (nested within trophic group) and the interactive effects between the response category and predictors (types of ecosystem, experimental study, plant life form, climatic zone) will be included in the model. Comparisons of the relative fit of these will again be assessed using a likelihood-ratio test. For example, the model with “trophic group + ecosystem type” will be compared to the base model with just trophic group, and the model with “trophic group + ecosystem type + trophic group × ecosystem type” will be compared to a model with “trophic group + ecosystem type”. To examine whether the mean effect sizes in the different categories differ significantly from zero, we will use t-values with associated 95% confidence intervals derived from the fitted meta-regression models. Note, data from greenhouse and other indoor experiments were removed from the models with climatic predictors.

Model	Question	Predictor variables
1	1	Trophic group
1.1A	2	Trophic group + Ecosystem type
1.1B	2	Trophic group + Ecosystem type + Trophic group × Ecosystem type
1.2A	2	Trophic group + Type of experimental study
1.2B	2	Trophic group + Type of experimental study + Trophic group × Type of experimental study
1.3A	2	Trophic group + Plant life form

1.3B	2	Trophic group + Plant life form + Trophic group × Plant life form
1.4A	2	Trophic group + Climatic zone type
1.4B	2	Trophic group + Climatic zone type + Trophic group × Climatic zone type
1.5A	1	Trophic group + log ₂ (added plant species richness over control)
1.5B	1	Trophic group + log ₂ (added plant species richness over control) + Trophic group × log ₂ (added plant species richness over control)
2	1	Trophic group response category
2.1A	2	Trophic group response category + Ecosystem type
2.1B	2	Trophic group response category + Ecosystem type + Trophic group response category × Ecosystem type
2.2A	2	Trophic group response category + Type of experimental study
2.2B	2	Trophic group response category + Type of experimental study + Trophic group response category × Type of experimental study
2.3A	2	Trophic group response category + Plant life form
2.3B	2	Trophic group response category + Plant life form + Trophic group response category × Plant life form
2.4A	2	Trophic group response category + Climatic zone type
2.4B	2	Trophic group response category + Climatic zone type + Trophic group response category × Climatic zone type
2.5A	1	Trophic group response category + log ₂ (added plant species richness over control)
2.5B	1	Trophic group response category + log ₂ (added plant species richness over control) + Trophic group response category × log ₂ (added plant species richness over control)

Table 1. The above table provides an overview of the meta-regression models that to be used to test the research hypothesis. The table gives the predictor variables included. Model 1 was nested within Model 1.1–1.5; and Model 2 was nested within Model 2.1–2.5. Ecosystem types included agroecosystems, grasslands and forests. Plant life form comprised herbaceous and woody plants. Climatic zone type was divided into tropical and temperate climatic zones. Type of experimental study was divided into plot and pot experiments. The response variable in all models will be the effect size of the responses of invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, weeds, plant-feeding nematodes, rodents and plants to the different comparison groups. Trophic group included invertebrate herbivores, plant diseases, weeds, plant-feeding nematodes, plant-consuming rodents and plants. Trophic group response category included invertebrate herbivore growth, herbivore reproduction, herbivore damage, plant disease reproduction, plant disease spread, plant disease damage, weed growth, weed reproduction, weed diversity, plant-feeding nematode reproduction, plant-feeding nematode damage, plant-consuming rodents reproduction, plant-consuming rodent damage, plant growth, plant reproduction, and plant quality. The model with suffix “A” is compared with base model (Model 1 or 2). The model with suffix “B” is compared with the nearest model with suffix “A”.

Regression analysis to assess the direct effect to the number of added plant species

To examine whether the number of added plant species richness results in additional explanatory power, a further analyses will be undertaken using the logarithm of plant species richness in the studies (e.g., log₂(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, ...)). Using this we will analyze the relationships between the number of added plant species richness and the different effect sizes along with fitted meta-regression lines. In these meta-regression analyses, we will treat the number of added plant species as a predictor and SMD as the response. This will be used to display the trend of SMD with the number of added plant species. The “lme()” function in the “nlme” library in R statistical environment will be used to fit a linear model using generalized least squares (Pinheiro, Bates & DebRoy 2007). Between-study heterogeneity will be explained in models using the function setting “random = list(~1 | Code)” in the call to lme(). The R function “rsq.lmm()” in the “rsq” library (Zhang, D. 2022) to calculate R-square from the model object.

Path analysis for plant species richness and the number of added plant species

Residual regression will be used to analyze the direct and indirect effects of binary plant species richness and number of added plant species richness on all interactions between plants and plant antagonists or between plants and various groups of plant antagonists, respectively. In this analysis we will use the log transformed ratio of means (ROM) as the response variable, which was calculated

$$\text{as } ROM_i = \log(M_{ii} / M_{ci}), 1 \leq i \leq m, \text{ and } sd_i = \sqrt{\frac{sd_{ii}^2}{n_{ii}M_{ii}^2} + \frac{sd_{ci}^2}{n_{ci}M_{ci}^2}}.$$

Specifically, following Emmenegger and Bühlmann (2023), the direct effect of plant antagonists on plants will be estimated by regressing the Pearson residuals extracted from the linear mixed-effects

model fitted with species richness and plant performance on the Pearson residuals extracted from the linear mixed-effects model fitted with species richness and plant antagonists performance. In summary, linear mixed-effects models will be conducted with the R function “lme” of the package “nlme”, with random intercepts for study IDs. Heteroscedasticity if present will be accounted for by providing fixed variances based on SMD and setting sigma to 1 in the lme call. We will use the residual regression to test the effects of plant species richness on each of the interactions between performance values of plants and herbivores, plants and diseases, plants and weeds, and plants and nematodes. We will also use residual regression to test the effects of plant species richness on the interactions between performance values of plants and the aggregate indicator (i.e., plant antagonists) in different ecosystems (i.e., terrestrial ecosystems, agroecosystems, grasslands and forests), as well as the effects of plant species richness on the interactions between plant performance and plant antagonist performance for different plant life forms (herbaceous and woody plants), climatic zones (temperate and tropical zones) and experiment types (i.e., plot and pot experiments). To measure the effects of varying levels of plant species richness, residual regression will be used to analyze the effects of the number of added plant species on the paired interactions between plants and herbivores, diseases, weeds or nematodes, respectively, as well as on the paired interactions between plants and plant antagonists in different ecosystems, plant life forms, climatic zones, and experiment types.

Assessing overall meta-analysis publication bias

We assessed publication bias using regression tests within which regression test value (partial slope) tests for an association between effect size and the sample variance will be quantified and a P (<0.05) significance value. We will follow Nakagawa and Santos (2012) whereby the residuals from different established models will be used to assess publication bias in mixed-effects meta-regression analysis. In this process we will consider SMD as a response variable. Different categories of trophic groups, ecosystems, plant life forms, climatic zones and experimental studies, as well as increased plant species richness will be considered as predictors in this process. Sampling variances will also be considered as an additional moderator in the mixed-effect model to test the publication bias. Moreover, we will report the Rosenberg (2005) fail-safe number to assess publication bias and compare this to an appropriate threshold.

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